

Early Detection of Neurotic Disorders and Study of its Impact Factors among Students of Medical Universities

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to the study of neurotic disorders, including emotional burnout syndrome, among medical university students at different stages of education. The research is based on the assumption that students at different stages of medical education exhibit differences in emotional-personal characteristics, social-psychological adaptation levels, and empathy. The aim of the study is to explore the psychological aspects of burnout syndrome in medical students at various stages of their professional education. To achieve this aim, methodologies to assess emotional-personal traits and social-psychological adaptation were employed. The study revealed differences in emotional-personal aspects and social-psychological adaptation levels. Additionally, it outlined directions for psycho-correctional and psycho-educational work with students, particularly regarding maladaptive adaptation strategies, stress coping methods, and negative perspectives about the future.

Keywords: neurotic disorders, emotional burnout syndrome, depression, motivation, depersonalization.

Introduction

In recent years, neurotic disorders, including emotional burnout syndrome (ESS), have been widely studied in the medical field. This syndrome is particularly prevalent in high-stress, high-pressure professions, including among medical students and doctors [1]. The term "burnout" (English - burnout) was introduced in the mid-1970s by American psychiatrist Herbert Freudenberger. This concept is defined as the deterioration of mental and physical health in healthy individuals engaged in close and intense contact with others[4].

ESS is a psychological state that includes emotional exhaustion, depersonalization (a sense of alienation from oneself and others), and a decrease in personal achievement. It is typically considered a job-related psychological syndrome that arises due to prolonged stress and high demands [3].

Studies have shown that ESS is more prevalent among medical students and healthcare workers than in the general population. For example, Shanafelt and colleagues found that the prevalence of ESS among medical students in the USA ranged from 17.6% to 82% [2]. According to the European conference (WHO, 2005), job-related stress is observed in one-third of workers in the European Union, which requires significant funds for treatment and affects the economies of the countries [5].

Objective of the Study

The main goal of this research is to examine the level of neurotic disorders, including emotional burnout syndrome, and the factors influencing it among medical university students. The study aims to explore the prevalence of emotional burnout syndrome, their emotional and personal traits, coping strategies for stress, and how the academic workload affects students' mental health.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted among students of the 4th and 5th years of the Faculty of Medicine at Tashkent Medical Academy. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) was used, which was adapted by H. Kuchkarov and N.F. Yadgarova for this study. This survey evaluates emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment levels. The study involved 71 students, 40 of whom (56.4%) were female, and 31 (43.6%) were male.

Among the students, 87.9% were aged 20-24, with an average age of 22.1 ± 0.8 years, while 12.1% were aged 25-29, with an average age of 27.1 ± 0.8 years. (picture 1)

(picture 1)

The distribution of marital status showed that 13 students (18.2%) were married, while 58 students (81.8%) were unmarried. 22.5% of the students had harmful habits (tobacco or alcohol consumption), and 77.5% did not have such habits. (picture 2)

(picture 2)

Results and Discussion

The survey results provided the following key indicators:

- Emotional Exhaustion:** 16.9% of students (12 students) often felt emotionally drained, while 73.1% (59 students) sometimes felt this way, indicating ongoing emotional exhaustion among students.
- Motivation and Depression:** 42.3% (30 students) occasionally felt exhausted and unmotivated to attend classes, while 57.7% (41 students) frequently experienced these feelings. This suggests that students often feel energy-deprived and demotivated in their academic work. (picture 3)

(picture 3)

- Personal Development and Depersonalization:** 28.2% (20 students) sometimes felt that their academic work made them a "tougher" person, while 71.8% (51 students) frequently felt this way, showing that their attitudes toward others were becoming more rigid.
- Social Alienation:** 40.8% (29 students) frequently wished to be alone, and 59.2% (43 students) sometimes wished for isolation. Additionally, 33.8% (24 students) sometimes wanted to be alone after classes, while 66.2% (47 students) frequently desired isolation, indicating tendencies toward social withdrawal and loneliness. (picture 4)

(picture 4)

5. **Hopelessness:** 35.2% (25 students) sometimes felt that their studies were making them more hopeless, reflecting a negative shift in their outlook on the future.

The academic workload, including lessons, practices, and theoretical exams, created persistent stress and psychological exhaustion among the students. Emotional burnout syndrome may develop as a result of ongoing exposure to this stressful environment. ESS can reduce interest in studies, decrease motivation, increase emotional exhaustion, and lead students to disengage from their work.

The study found that ESS was present at both low (L) and moderate (M) levels, indicating that students are in the early stages of emotional burnout, which may intensify over time. Recommendations for improving psychological support and mechanisms to alleviate stress in the academic process were proposed, including stress management training, time for rest and sports, and promoting social activities to improve students' mental well-being.

Conclusion

The study concludes that emotional burnout syndrome is widespread among medical students, leading to high levels of stress, emotional exhaustion, and hopelessness. ESS negatively affects students' well-being, reduces their interest in studies, and may impact their future careers. Therefore, it is essential to strengthen preventive measures, provide psychological support, and optimize academic workloads to create a healthier and more supportive environment for medical students, which will improve their academic performance and better prepare them for their future professional lives.

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